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Continuing Education as a Teachers' Professional Culture Component

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Abstract

The relevance of the research problem of modern approaches to forming and development of the teacher's professional culture in the conditions of informatization and digitalization of the educational environment is caused by the necessity of continuing education and raising its quality.

In this connection, the present paper is directed to the study of the potential of modern ICT as a resource of the teachers' professional development in the process of their continuing education.

The leading method in this problem study is the method of generalization of domestic and foreign researches results in the field of continuing education, and analysis of the up-to-date experience, modern pedagogical practices of using innovative technologies making it possible to disclose successfulness of forming the teacher's informational and communicative culture. Research data and results of questioning 525 pedagogues are expounded supporting the necessity of forming new possible instruments of developing pedagogical culture.

The paper deals with some peculiarities of modern approaches to forming and developing the teacher's professional culture within the frames of supplementary professional education as a component of continuing education. Included are the results of empirical research of an influence of the use by teachers of educational organizations modern informational and communicative technologies aimed at positive interaction in a collective body.

Practical significance of the research results, presented in the paper is in the proof of effectiveness of implementing variable module programs aimed at teaching pedagogues the mediation technology and the technology of joint digital model-building electronic aids.

As a result of the research, it has been asserted that integration of the informative-communicative component while developing professional culture and orienting educational process to expanding knowledge alongside informational, socio-psychological and upbringing aspects in the teacher's activity, it is possible to ascertain successfulness of raising the quality of education, a positive motivation for using the competencies acquired and broadening the potentialities of the educational environment.

Keywords: continuing education, teacher's professional culture, informational technologies, communicative technologies, co-construction, joint model-building technology of digital aids, conflict resolution technology, mediation.

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Introduction

Research actuality of the problem of continuing education as teachers' professional culture component

As reacted by the processes of globalization, doing away economic, social, cultural boundaries and, consequently, strengthening competition, modern specialists have to be mobile and competitive. It dictates the necessity of constant bringing up of one's qualification in accordance with the market's demands, life-long education and leads to attaching importance to the development of all existing educational systems.

Nowadays a system of continuing education has to correspond to the needs of the country and to the tendencies of trade development of the world labour market, being one of the primary strategic goals of the national system of education (Lomakina & Pisarenko; 2020; Üreten et al., 2017).

The National education doctrine, the Concept of organization of the system of adult continuing education in the Russian Federation for the period until 2025 (The State Programme of the Russian Federation "Development of Education" for 2018-2025) and other system-building documents form demands to a principally new paradigm of continuing education, which presupposes a constant renovation, individualization of demand and possibilities of their satisfaction. The key feature of such education becomes not only transfer of knowledge and technology transfer, but formation of creative competences, readiness to be re- instructed and develop professional culture.

This, in its turn, elevates one to the primary problem of raising the quality of professional education based on the modern context of digitalization and educational modernization. And this, first of all, refers to the educational environment, which must flexibly react to the constantly changing conditions and respond to the demands of the effectiveness of the educational potential of the whole system. In this connection, an undisputable opinion seems to be that of modern researchers on the point, that "...one of the key figures of the system of education is the teacher, who must orient him/herself in his/her activity on raising the quality of education and consolidate efforts on solving most important and concrete tasks of education and upbringing bearing in mind that "...the modern teacher is not only a subject of professional activity, but also the direct participant of political and socio-cultural processes taking place in modern society" (Sorokopud & Sirotna, 2020, p. 188).

Constantly, activation of the cultural-creative function of modern education strengthens the role and significance of the teacher – a vehicle of cultural traditions, a professional who secures not only a simple transition of ready-made knowledge necessary for the growing child, but also develops personality in each pupil. Changes in socio-cultural and economic life of the society demand a qualitative transformation of the teacher's activity in the professional field, deepening his/her mobility and openness.

Speaking of demands to the modern teacher delineated in legal normative and research methodological documents (Federal Law "On education in the Russian Federation" No. 273-FZ, 2017) we see that today we need a specialist, who cooperates successfully and productively in the educational environment, possesses skills of applying modern technologies of teaching and upbringing, who can operatively react in conditions of globalization in education, quickly adapts in the environment, that is one who belongs to multifactorial character

of tasks and changes, who belongs to pedagogical culture, who shakes traditions and new tendencies in these spheres of knowledge, who can conceptually substantiate his/her activity (Farnieva et al., 2020).

A high level of professional culture makes it possible not only to fully disclose new contents of education, but also to promote culturally oriented interaction among all the participants of the teaching-upbringing process (Lykova et al., 2018).

According to Ivanova, it is important for modern pedagogic “to provide in a complex way for the peculiarities of the media epoch, of modern post-industrial environment globalizing the world” (2016, pp. 61-68). Thus, one of the main factors which manifests itself in forming orientation, values, motivation, principles of behavior and activity of a pedagogue, is the teacher’s professional culture, which, in its turn, makes it as an inseparable component in raising the quality of the educational process.

The foregoing makes it possible to state that today among the immediate problems of educational development is the problem of studying up-to-date approaches to forming and developing the teacher’s professional culture in the atmosphere of informatics and digitalization, which has preconditioned our research.

Purpose and objectives of the study

Purpose of the study is to empirically test the effectiveness of modern information-communication technology (ICT) as a resource of developing the teachers’ professionalism in the process of their continuing education.

Literature review

Teachers’ professional development in modern educational environment

Teachers’ professional development in modern educational environment is one of the most actual directions of domestic and foreign research. The process of standardization and renovation of the Russian education system makes it necessary to work out new tools of improving teachers’ professional activity and culture. Research analysis allows one to confirm that, with foreign colleagues, “...the accent shifted towards the practical aspect (professional changes under the influence of different factors); while our native researchers, alongside the practice, study in their work also the theoretical aspect of the problem (methodological approaches, ways of professional development)” (Goglova, 2015, pp. 134-138).

Examining multifaceted problem of formation of teachers professional culture and supporting ourselves on the essence of the term “professional culture” in the works of Gaisina (2002), Zhiluayeva (2008), Zaretskaya (2012), Sitnik & Krupina (2007), Sorokopud & Sirotina (2020) and others, we can state that teachers professional culture “... appears as one of socially meaningful indicators of a person’s education, reflecting a combination of spiritual and material values, a degree of creative self-realization and actualization” (Sorokopud & Sirotina, 2020; Sitnik & Krupina, 2007, pp. 187-189).

In today's education, we need such a teacher who cooperates successfully and productively with all the participants of the educational process, who possesses modern educational technologies, can speedily react and adapt oneself. A modern teacher is ideally thought of as a follower of pedagogical culture, acquainted with traditions and new tendencies in these spheres of knowledge, who can conceptually substantiate his or her activity. That is why working out a technology of teaching grown-up people who are actively involved in professional activity, developing their creative potential is becoming a global pedagogical problem today.

Consequently, innovations and continuity in the modern system of education are gaining the character of necessity, and incorporation of teachers into innovative processes presupposes constant raising of their qualification throughout all their professional activity.

According to Sitnik and Krupina, "teachers' professional culture is a complex of general culture and professional knowledge in all directions of educational activity: theory and methods of subject being taught, pedagogy as a study of up-bringing, age and social psychology, psychology of pedagogical work, age physiology, the basics of hygiene and medicine, basics ethics and aesthetics, practical economy and ecology, sociology and philosophy, use of electronic appliances - and a skill to apply those in pedagogical practice" (as cited in Pokhmelkina & Semenov, 2008, pp. 121-138). This is the evidence of the fact that raising professional level cannot be only limited by questions of methods of teaching the subjects employed. It is necessary to fill the contents of raising qualification with those questions that will secure development of professional culture as a whole.

Therefore, one of the main factors of renovating the educational system is a necessity to improve effectiveness of the learning process with a permanent specialist, scholarly methodological accompaniment, providing its demand for raising professional qualification.

Modern approaches to developing teachers' professional competences

Basing ourselves on the above-stated, we consider the teachers' professional culture as a complex of general culture and professional competencies alongside all directions of pedagogical activity: pedagogics as a study of upbringing, theory and methods of the subjects taught, age and social psychology, psychology of pedagogical work, age physiology, the basics of hygiene and medicine, the basics of psychology, ethics and aesthetics, practical economy and ecology, sociology and philosophy, use of ICT, and so on, and above all, readiness and skills to apply those fields of knowledge in pedagogical practice.

A model of teachers' personal professional competencies at the modern stage presupposes inclusion of the components presented in Table 1.

Table 1. A model of teachers' professional competencies

Key pedagogical competencies	Basic pedagogical competencies	Definition
Personal	Subject	A quality of the teacher's actions making it possible to carry out the educational process. The contents and methodological components be included.
	Methodical	A quality of the teacher's actions, reflecting the readiness to secure an optimal level of organization of the educational process in correspondence with modern demands, and also the readiness for continuous raising their qualifications, mastering diverse pedagogical technologies, generalization and transmission of their own experience.
Inter-personal	Interactive-communicative	The quality of the teacher's actions ensuring a possibility to build up relations with participants of the educational process, based on mutual understanding and collaboration; ability to work in groups, to take on social and ethical obligations; ability to publicly represent the results of one's professional activity.
	Perceptive	Ability to orientate oneself in one's relations with those surrounding one, concern about reactions of other people, as to one's actions in specific situations, ability to consider real consequences of one's behavior.
	Communicative-informative	A quality of teacher's actions, which is expressed in a complex of knowledge, skills, habits and automatic sets in one's interaction with the communicative-informative environment.
Social	General culture	Includes a range of questions which the teacher must be well informed of, have knowledge and practical experience: peculiarities of human culture; spiritual and moral basis of man's life and mankind, different nations; culturological basis of family, social, public phenomena and traditions; the role of science and religion in human life, their influence on the world; competences in everyday life and socio-recreation time.
	Social-pedagogical	Is characterized as: ability and skill to function in the society, to know its problems, to understand the activity mechanisms of its activity; social activity and socially oriented projects; complex of social maturity, social orientation, social adaptability, social mobility and social effectivity.
	Legal	The quality of the teacher's actions ensuring effective use in professional activity legal and other normative documents of the authorities necessary to solve professional tasks.
Reflexive	Psychological	Maximum adequate, proportional combination of the teacher's professional, communicative, personal qualities which allows to achieve qualitative results in the process of teaching.
	Personal-developing	Skills development in the sphere of self-improvement, self-regulation, self-development, personal and subject reflection: meaning of life; professional development; language and speech development, mastering the culture of one's native language, mastering foreign language.

As the table above shows, to bring about conditions of learners' psychological comfort and security, meet their demands by means of social, legal, medical, psychological, pedagogical mechanisms, to prevent and overcome negative phenomena in the educational organization, the family, the nearest environment and other groups of people, teachers must be able to permanently renew and expand the knowledge and practical skills at hand.

Besides, according to Yamburg (2019), teachers must understand the language of their "adjacent specialists (neighbours)": psychologists, defectologists, social pedagogues and others so that they could translate it into a pedagogical action. This makes it necessary for teachers to learn new psycho-pedagogical methods and technologies.

Modern informational and communicative technologies potential as a resource for teachers' professional development in the process of their continuing education.

Research by both foreign and domestic investigators has shown that teacher's personality is transformed in the process of his/her activity. Being the subject of educational relations, he/she interacts with all the participants of the teaching-upbringing process. Analyzing the data, it is also possible to maintain that to build up the teacher's identity supposes a continuous process, and its development constantly changes because of the teaching experience and social interactions. Besides, the results demonstrate that formation of one's own pedagogical style does not always take place without conflict. Conflicts appear both in the process of interaction with subjects of educational environment and in the process of one's own professional formation. And their timely and correct solution leads one to a new understanding of pedagogical identity and provides new possibilities for professional development (Villegas et al., 2020).

In its turn, a well-shaped demand for professional development and raising pedagogical culture are conducive for shortening disagreement between motivation for renovating knowledge and progressively ageing learning material in the process of rapid development of science, technique, means of communications. And that implies striving for incessant self-development, improving one's qualification and mastery, realization of special means, methods and techniques of obtaining new knowledge and use of acquired competences in practice. And this, in its turn, requires transition to a new level of supplementary professional education curricula (qualification improvement and retraining), meeting a constantly growing demand for actual information and effective means of its treatment (Maksimova, 2012).

That is why it is necessary today to teach the pedagogue new communicative techniques, such as mediation (a technology of conflict resolution in the educational setting), co-construction and co-reflection (a technology of professional communication and designing educational processes).

In particular, Grasel et al. (2006), Meta & Pokhmelkin (2004), Oborotova (2015), Pokhmelkina & Semenov (2008), Hertel (2016), Shamlkashvili (2014) define mediation as constructive technology of conflict resolution in society. Reusser (2001), Schön (1983), Kopoteva et al. (2018) consider co-construction as a productive dialogue inside a team, as effective addition to professional competencies and preserving a high motivational ingredient while assimilating innovative components and mutual model-building of the learning process.

Bearing in mind a confirmed efficiency and a potential of modern information-communication technologies, we have decided it necessary to teach pedagogues those technologies with the contents of curricula for qualification improvement and re-training (Kopoteva & Merzlikina, 2020; Khodakova & Oborotova, 2015).

Methodology

Teachers professional culture development with the help of mediation and co-construction technologies.

The aim of the research: to study the potential of modern information-communication technology (ICT) as a resource of developing the teachers' professionalism in the process of their continuing education.

Methods: generalization and analysis of the available experience, of modern educational IT practices which make it possible to disclose the degree of progress of forming the teacher's informational and communicative culture, generalization of results of methodical and pedagogical research in the sphere.

Experimental base of the research

More than 500 teachers (of all the levels of general education) from educational organizations of Moscow, Moscow region, Novosibirsk, Lipetsk and Lipetsk region took part in the research in the frame of corporative education by differentiated module programs: "Mediation approach to the peculiarities of interaction of the participants of the educational process", "Modern socio-pedagogical, psychological and juvenile directions in teachers' activity", "The unified IT environment of the educational organization" (designed by Oborotova and Khodakova), "Joint technology of model-building of IT education" (designed by Merzlikina). All these courses were used both as independent disciplines and as part of larger programmes of supplementary professional education (re-training and qualification development) from 2010 till 2019.

Results

Stages of the experiment

Certification experiment

Realization of co-construction by means of the electronic systems joint model-building technology.

Pedagogues engaged in research on the use of teaching aids in the education system have proved that the teaching process becomes intensive when it makes use of visual aids. Interactive IT aids have much more didactic possibilities than paper made. As the data of questionnaire survey carried out in 2018-2019 among Russian junior class teachers with the help of Google forms show, many teachers (85% of those questioned) apply electronic visual aids (interactive lectures, tables, charts, illustrations, interactive diagnostic tests and others), 60% of them use ready-made digital visual aids, produced by different publishing houses.

It is important to note that there are teachers who make their own visual aids taking into account their work and the age of the learners.

Questioning teachers and research in the field of joint IT model-building by IT have shown that purposeful work is necessary on the basis of a technology specially offered by the author thereof. It has been revealed that an optimal form of this kind of activity can be a system of lessons, including different stages of children's readiness to joint model-building of IT visual aids. The essence of the author's technology consists in developing the teacher's professional culture in the sphere of applying IT technologies in the educational process.

While constructing a new technology of joint IT model-building, the experience of carrying out similar work (using IT media for developing pupils' sense reading) was taken into account (Kopoteva & Merzlikina, 2020).

Realization of mediation

To form and to develop communicative competencies, in particular, to master the skill of preventing and solving conflicts in an educational environment (mediation technology), we elaborated and approbated different module programs: “Mediation approach to peculiarities of interaction with the participants of an educational process”, “Modern socio-pedagogical, psychological and juvenile approaches to the teachers’ activity” and “Joint informative-communicative environment of an educational organization”.

The modules include theoretical and practice-oriented material conducive to developing skills and habits of applying mediation technology to the educational process and forming mediate culture of the learner. The main educational aim is focused on motivation for continuing professional-personified development and mastering innovative technologies of accompanying a person in the educational environment which are necessary for teachers’ practical activity in their diagnostic, correction, prevention work with children, adolescents, young people and adults.

At the verification stage more than 80% of teachers at the input survey pointed out to the significance of the skills as to solve conflicts and to possess the ability to prevent conflict situations in modern reality (Farnieva et al., 2020).

Formative experiment

Co-construction realization

In the process realization of the experimental work the main purpose was bringing to light the effectiveness of the joint model-building technology of the IT teaching aids in the process of realization of the educational programs attached to the subject “The basics of religious cultures and civic ethics” and to discovering the teacher’s and the learners’ parts in their joint activity at each stage of the work, which implies a necessity to develop the teacher’s professional culture.

In the process of the formative experiment, we worked at development and approbation of the modern-building technology of IT teaching aids in the process of the teacher’s and student’s joint activity within the frame of educational problem “The basics of religious culture and civic ethics” (designed by Merzlikina). At the base of the author’s technology was laid the algorithm of developing the teacher professional culture: (“Teacher-Activity-Student”).

Structure of the teacher’s activity (it was defined by Kuzmina) consists of five functional components: 1) gnostic; 2) projective; 3) constructive; 4) communicative; 5) organisational (Kuzmina, 1970). The present structuration corresponds to the achievement of goals and joint work of the teacher and the students under the condition of IT model-building. At the same time, the structure proposed by Kuzmina needs a certain concretization, which takes into account, first, the joint teacher’s and students’ activity and secondly, the planned result of this activity – digital aid.

At the first stage the teacher must have knowledge not only in the sphere of his/her subject, but also in the specifics of communication while working with electronic gadgets and a degree of the students' readiness for this kind of work, and take into account their age interests.

The second component is projective. It supposes that teachers have certain ideas about strategies and ways of achieving learning results with the help of IT visual aids.

The third component is constructive. When a joint model-building of the teaching aids is in progress, the teacher must work out a system of lessons, including students, independent research, team-work, consultation, a joined discussion with the students both intermediate stages and the final result of activity, that is the electronic gadget.

The fourth component is communicative. The specifics of communication while independent construction of a digital tool under the teacher's guidance is based on the teacher's professional communicative skills with due regard for the specifics of work with electronic media.

The fifth component implies organization of the teacher's work and realization his/her ability to activate students' work with the new source of information.

Such work was carried out during construction of electronic aids while studying the subject "The basics of religious culture and civic ethics (BRCCE)". This particular subject was not chosen by chance. Addressing spiritual-moral problems in the life of society, its spiritual-moral enlightenment has become one of the ideological goals of the state policy.

More so that some scientists, for instance the academician Akimov (1998), come to the conclusion that it is "the spiritual imperative that is the only criterion of man survival in the third millennium". The revival of spiritual-moral education going back with its roots into the deepest history is realized nowadays in two main directions: introduction into the special subjects ("The basics of world religion", "The basics of civic ethics") and integration of spiritual-moral education into different school subjects. The problem of such subjects' introduction into the curriculum was taken up by Franko (2014), Pimenova (2010), Vinogradova (2015), Zharkovskaya et al. (2007) and many others. These specifics of this subject carrying a huge humanitarian potential from different spaces: psychology, sociology, history, religion, ethics, aesthetics, philosophy etc., an emotional-cognitional richness of the material makes it possible to influence the conscious and sub-conscious spheres of the student's personality (Pimenova, 2010, pp. 138-160).

To reach the subject goals we chose the theme "Customs of the society". Aspects of studying this theme represented in the course are as follows: disclosing the notions "customs", "society". To solve the tasks of the course, it is expedient to construct such digital tool as digital table "The customs of the society". Such a form of representing the teaching stuff was not chosen by chance: a table is a structured text which makes provision for grouping and systematization.

The advantages of a digital table lie in the fact that it can be used many times over, there is a possibility to address the sources (vocabulary, encyclopedic articles, fiction texts, video- and audio materials and many

others). Materials of digital tables can be used while designing summative testing and carrying out corrective work if it needs to be.

Undoubtedly, children, as users, have long been acquainted with the use of interactive teaching tools and know the specifics of work with them. Joint activity over the construction of the table includes a number of stages: 1) discussion of the aims of the work; 2) choice of the form of presentation of the information (selection of headings, the main text, illustrative material if needed, hyper-reference texts); 3) proceeding of the material (information transfer from one form to another); 4) design; 5) approbation.

At the first stage the teacher's part consists of organization – to activate the children's attention and motivate them to constructing a joint digital tool.

At the second stage the teacher must correct the children's activity as to the choice of the type of visuality by means of questions and tasks (Which form do you think is purposeful? Why? How many columns? How many lines? What words do you choose as main? What visual aids do you need? Will there be hyper-texts references in the table? And so on).

At the third stage there is shaping of all the material.

The fourth stage is the table design. Under the teacher's guidance, one of the pupils drew the table on the traditional blackboard, another one constructed it on an interactive board, in the program PowerPoint (Microsoft), using SmartArt tools.

The result of the joint work of the teacher and the children was a digital table "Customs of the society". At the end, the teacher suggests that they should compare the table with one, made by a professional publisher. The aim of the comparison: analysis of the children's activity.

At this stage it was proved that the technology of joint model-building electronic aids is a result of teacher's professional activity lining up a trajectory of ways and means for improving the children's level of knowledge in the field of using IT communication technology in educational environment.

Realization of mediation

Mediation, among other things, is an effective technology of solving disputes among different levels of a large collective body the instruction of which results in a general improvement of the situation in the group, where everybody – a child, the teacher, a parent – becomes to feel more protected (Maksimova, 2012).

Development of the mediative components in the teacher's professional culture is aimed at forming special interactive skills in conflict situations, knowledge of the specifics of rendering mediate aid (while regulation conflicts), skills of teaching children, parents, colleagues to effective interaction based on the principles of positive communication.

In the process of qualification improvement teachers are taught according to module principle, where all the peculiarities of the native education system, the culture of inter-school and family relations, many other factors meaningful for securing effectiveness, are taken into consideration.

The goals of education are elaboration of a neutral position and development of the mediator's professional identity. It is realized at lectures and practical studies by means of discovering and approbation of new and unusual points of view on conflicts and life situations (Lomakina & Pisarenko, 2020). More attention is paid first of all to the internal position and to reflective skills.

Mediation is joined to strategies traditional in culture and society, of solving conflict, enriching them by specific technics and methods, thanks to the following peculiarities:

- 1) a special approach to the conflict in which the interests of each person are protected;
- 2) acknowledgement of priority, responsibility and self-decision of each participant of the process;
- 3) emphasis on the subjects' resources, rights and duties;
- 4) orientation on finding agreement;
- 5) acknowledgement of changeability of agreements' in everyday life;
- 6) adaptive flexibility in making decisions, which are carried out in life as they meet the interests of all the parties of a conflict and to real conditions (Maksimova, 2012).

The mediation procedure in an educational environment has certain stages:

The first stage is informational.

It is expedient to take into account the three levels of analysis of the sides in disagreement while preparing and carrying on the mediation process:

- 1) concrete positions;
- 2) needs and interests;
- 3) meaning and orientation.

The second stage is working out variants.

After the parties have received the necessary information and defined what is important for each party, the mediator can help them to work out some variants for solving the dispute. It becomes the fundamental stage for clearing the whole range of possibilities. The mediator must hereby oppose a possible striving of either of the parties to consider their proposal the only version of solution possible.

The third stage is analysis and evaluation of the decisions proposed.

Finally, it is important for the parties to analyse the decisions offered concerning the degree of their correspondence to their needs and interests. The mediator's task is to bring about a context in which each party will regard each variant not only from the point of view by which it meets the needs and interests of each party, but also considering how far it takes into account the needs and interests of the other party.

The fourth stage is taking a decision.

After that both parties choose the means of decision about different questions. It is important that any agreement achieved on this or that aspect of a dispute should be regarded as preliminary, liable to verification within the limits of solving all the questions, and not one of the parties should accept any of the agreements achieved as unconditional.

The mediator is under the stress of defeat and apprehension of "disadvantageous decisions", which do not allow the parties of the conflict to listen to each other and to overthink possible agreements. Thus, as a result of mediation activity the process of discussion is protected from disintegration. That process is guided in such a way as to keep up an ability to be in conference and be respectful to each other. Mediators direct the process of discussion in such a way as to recreate again and again an "expanse of hope" and a perspective of achieving a decision that would suit everyone, an expanse in which it is possible to freely exchange ideas and accept another person's point of view (Maksimova, 2012).

As a result of instruction, the teacher's capacities are formed to carrying out mediation activity in an educational organization, practical skills of a mediator (Art, 2007) are acquired, which allows one to effectively solve disputes and conflicts, to react constructively in a critical situation, and to respect the personality of each other (Villegas et al., 2020).

Summing up

At the stage of the experiment control, 65% of respondents noted that the skills of applying the mediation technology allowed them alongside with solving diversified conflicts in the educational-upbringing system, carry out prophylactic and correction work aimed at the prevention of violence, aggression and asocial forms of behavior among children, adolescents and young people.

Analysis of the experimental work results has revealed positive dynamics of the teacher's professional development in the process of teaching modern ICT.

Thus, making use of modern approaches to forming and development of teachers' professional culture in the process of getting their continuing education within the frames of supplementary professional programs is an effective way of developing positive personal interaction skills in the society.

Discussions

Thus, we can confirm some correlation between peculiarities of media epoch and the necessity of new decisions for building up socially comfortable educational process; a correlation between the influence of educational process continuity and the growth of motivational-valuable approach to professional communication; development of the teacher's professional mastery, his/her informational and communicational culture on the basis of modern approaches to schooling with orientation to all levels of Russian education and prognosticated improvement of the upbringing-educational process in accordance with demands of educational and professional standards, widening possibilities of constant methodological assistance and development of the specialists' professional competencies.

Conclusion

According to the results of our research, it is possible to maintain that by means of integration of information-communication component to the process of development of the professional orientation to widening knowledge of informational, socio-psychological and upbringing aspects of the teacher's activity, one can state successfulness of the quality of the educational process, a positive motivation to use competencies received and widening of the possibilities of all the institutions which take part in the person's education and upbringing: family – pre-school organization – school – higher institution.

Intensification of forming the teacher's project and construction skills by means of modern ICT, such as mediation and joint ICT model-building is a result of upbringing educational process being successful.

Modern teacher's pedagogical culture widens with competencies which make it possible to use ICT for organizing different students' activity. Those are such competencies that are connected with educational processes modelling by means of ICT (awareness of the place; meaning and part played by ICT in organizing effective activity; knowledge of psychological peculiarities of ICT reception; ability to construct the process of organization on the basis of integration of traditional and innovative teaching aids).

Besides, mastering ICT by teacher broadens the borders of communication both of the teacher and the learner, which provides not only effectivity of the teaching-learning process, but also brings about a favourable atmosphere for the participants thereof.

Formation of a member of communicative skills, provided by means of ICT is inductive, alongside solving differently oriented conflicts in the educational-upbringing system, for carrying out prophylactic and correction work aimed at preventing violence, aggressive, asocial forms of behavior among children, adolescents and youth.

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